

**University of St. Cyril and Methodius" - Faculty of Medicine - Skopje
Undergraduate Studies in General Medicine**

OBESITY: PUBLIC HEALTH ASPECTS

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07-11-2025, Skopje

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ABSTRACT:

Obesity is a critical public health issue worldwide, and it is highly associated with chronic diseases as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, various types of cancer, and metabolic-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD). In this paper, a comprehensive overview is presented on obesity's multifactorial public health aspects, which are disease burden, psychosocial consequences, economic costs, and effects on life expectancy. While obesity's prevalence has nearly doubled (in comparison with 3 decades before) and continues its increasing rate year by year, and mortality rates are rising at an alarming rate, it is crucial to underscore the urgency of effective management of this public health struggle. Childhood obesity is also a major concern when researching obesity, as it's closely connected with adult obesity, as long as children are suffering from chronic diseases from such a young age. The paper discusses about the impact of obesity not only in public health but also in an inclusive way its impact in society and concludes with thoughts about obesity and recommendations for the control and regulation of obesity.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is a major problem for public health which affects severe the health and wellbeing and is associated with chronic diseases as diabetes and cardiovascular etc. (1,2). For the identification of obesity, usage of the metric unit "Body mass index" (BMI) as it is presented by the World Health Organization (WHO) is crucial. BMI is weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared. (2,3) The limits by category can be differ depending on the region of interest such as Western Pacific Region, Europe and North America region etc. (4). In the European and North American region an adult, with a BMI of 25.0 to 29.9 kg/m² is defined as overweight and with a BMI of 30 kg/m² or higher is defined as obese (5,6).

In more detail, as mentioned earlier obesity is closely associated with chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, stroke, type 2 diabetes, various cancers, osteoarthritis, sleep apnea, respiratory diseases and liver diseases. (2,6,7)

The management and control of obesity is very difficult and demanding due to numerus public health aspects. To understand better what public health aspects are, is considered useful to define what public health is. Public health is a common term used by healthcare specialists; public health is an important tool for keeping the nation healthy as well as its development (8).

The primary public health concerns associated with obesity can be summarized as follows: disease burden, psychosocial impacts, economic consequences, demographic effects on life expectancy, and issues related to childhood obesity. (2,6,7)

- (2,6,7) **Psychosocial problems** have also been noticed in people with obesity. These problems affect negative their overall well-being. They commonly experience higher levels of anxiety, depression and bullying, these have direct

impact to their social life as they suffer from alienation and lower overall social-life quality. (9)

- **The economic impact** is also huge as obesity is a major medical costly problem. It's estimated that direct medical costs in the United States alone regarding obesity-affected patients reaching approximately \$173 billion annually. (10)
 - **Life expectancy** is also being threatened by the rising prevalence of obesity. Obesity's linking with chronic medical issues is very usual, it is noted that chronic obese people have very few disease-free years compared to those maintaining a healthy weight. (9-11)
- Childhood obesity** must also be noted as it is increasing in annual basis. Childhood obesity is also associated with increased risks of adult obesity, metabolic diseases and mental health issues and that highlights the reason why obesity must be prevented from an early stage. (2,7)

A significant amount of research within the last years has been made about obesity and its aspects in public health. Most of those researches focus in one aspect of public health, so for us it's crucial to highlight the significance and severeness of obesity as a public health problem.

The goal of this research paper is to present the public health aspects of obesity summarized and as they have given to the research community by numerous of research papers, books and articles. (12)

2. METHODS:

We conducted a comprehensive review of the literature, research for scientific papers in the databases PubMed and Google Scholar, using the following keywords: obesity, cancer, MAFLD, depression, economy, childhood obesity, public health aspects, prevalence of obesity, Death rate, most linked to our research topic. We did a screening read research papers and research articles to expand our knowledge on the topic and be able to collect the data needed in order to present them in better detail. The criteria for the data collection and choice of articles were mostly matching keywords and research papers in English, published in the last 10 years. Additionally, data from the WHO's website and Our World Data and by collecting their data we calculated the averages and came to the results presented.

Data is presented using the descriptive method. presenting our data in a descriptive way, in an analytical way and also used statistical methods, analyzing data through the years to calculate the average values in order to come to conclusions and results for discussion of the charts.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Prevalence of adults obesity

As shown on chart 1 adult obesity has dramatically increased throughout the years, since 1990 the prevalence in all regions (defined by WHO) increased approximately by 20%, except in Europe which seems to increase in only by approximately 10%. This

considering other actions Europe did such as promotion of the Mediterranean diet, setting physical goals at least by 150 minutes aerobic exercise per week and modest weight loss targets indicates that Europe compared to other WHO regions has done better management of the disease.(13,14)

Chart 1, (13)

Share of adults who are overweight or obese

"Overweight" is defined here as a body mass index (BMI) above 25. BMI is a person's weight in kilograms divided by their height in meters squared.

Data source: World Health Organization - Global Health Observatory (2025)

OurWorldinData.org/obesity | CC BY

Note: To allow for comparisons between countries and over time, this metric is age-standardized¹.

1. Age standardization Age standardization is an adjustment that makes it possible to compare populations with different age structures, by standardizing them to a common reference population.

Read more: [How does age standardization make health metrics comparable?](#)

3.2 Mortality attributed to obesity

In terms of death rates from obesity, as shown in Chart 2, we follow an overall increase in the last three decades with regional differences. Death rate has increased from 1990 to 2021 in the Americas just only by 5%, in western pacific by 31%, in Eastern Mediterranean by 40%, in African region by 48% and in south-east Asia surprisingly by 83%. Meanwhile European region had a significant decrease of 11%, which highlights even more the battling against obesity considering the measures taken, as mentioned before with an addition of regular monitoring waist circumference in addition to weight as visceral fat is a strong predictor of cardiometabolic risk and communication with empathy and motivational interviewing to support behavioral change. (14,15) In 2021, the highest mortality rates are observed in the Eastern Mediterranean region, 100 deaths attributed to obesity per 100.000 population, whilst the lowest in Western Pacific region, 25 deaths per 100.000 people.

Chart 2, (15)

Death rate from obesity, 1990 to 2021

Estimated annual number of deaths attributed to obesity¹ per 100,000 people.

Data source: IHME, Global Burden of Disease (2024)

OurWorldinData.org/obesity | CC BY

Note: To allow for comparisons between countries and over time, this metric is age-standardized². Obesity is defined as having a body-mass index (BMI) ≥ 30 . BMI is a person's weight (in kilograms) divided by their height (in meters) squared.

1. Obesity Obesity is defined as having a body-mass index (BMI) above 30.

A person's BMI is calculated as their weight (in kilograms) divided by their height (in meters) squared. For example, someone measuring 1.60 meters and weighing 64 kilograms has a BMI of $64 / 1.6^2 = 25$.

Obesity increases the mortality risk of many conditions, including cardiovascular disease, gastrointestinal disorders, type 2 diabetes, joint and muscular disorders, respiratory problems, and psychological issues.

2. Age standardization Age standardization is an adjustment that makes it possible to compare populations with different age structures, by standardizing them to a common reference population.

Read more: [How does age standardization make health metrics comparable?](#)

3.2.1

Comorbidities

One of the most critical mortality indicators is the link between obesity and chronic diseases with high mortality rate. The most common being Metabolic Associated Fatty Liver Disease (MAFLD), Cancer and depression. (16–18) These also construct the risk factors of obesity.

3.2.1.1 MAFLD - It's a chronic liver condition where an excessive amount of fat is gathered inside the liver. More specifically, it's defined when the content of the liver cells is more than 5% fat. The Pathogenesis of MAFLD has many factors such as imbalance between the synthesis and degradation of triglycerides in hepatocytes, insulin resistance, pro-inflammatory factors, oxidative stress, and disturbances in lipid metabolism. Obesity contributes directly to MAFLD due to its ability of promoting insulin resistance and adipose tissue inflammation causing increased synthesis and delivery of fatty acids directly to the liver.(16)

3.2.1.2 Cancer - It's a disease in which somatic cells undergo numerous alterations causing them to grow and multiply uncontrollably. This disruption of the normal

coordination of cell growth with nutrient availability allows abnormal cancer cells to multiply even at times when such growth would be normally suppressed by the human system. Cancer growth can be triggered due to high exposure to mutation factors in the daily life of the individual, such examples are chemicals, radiation and other biological agents. The link between cancer and obesity has many different features. Obesity contributes to the creation of a cancer-beneficial environment with nutrient excess, chronic low-grade inflammation, high levels of insulin, insulin-like growth factors (IGF), leptin, and altered adipokines.(17)

3.2.1.3 Depression - A complex psychiatric disorder characterized by persistent low mood, anhedonia, and cognitive disturbances. Its pathophysiology consists of multiple dysregulated systems of our biological whole including genetic susceptibility, neuroendocrine abnormalities such as hyperactivation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis resulting in elevated cortisol, chronic low-grade inflammation marked by increased pro-inflammatory cytokines, and altered neuroimmune signaling pathways. Obesity and depression are linked due to shared biological pathways. Obesity causes pro-inflammatory cytokines that in many cases affect brain function and promote depressive symptoms. Also, insulin and leptin resistance commonly observed in obesity cause disturbance in energy balance regulation contributing to aberrant appetite and mood regulation seen in depression.(18)

Other public health aspects of obesity as mentioned in the introduction are disabilities connected to obesity, poor life quality, economic impact and low life expectancy.(19–22)

3.3 Quality life in individuals with obesity and disabilities connected with obesity

Many disabilities are linked with obesity; examples range from muscular-skeletal conditions and mental health disorders to learning disabilities. Obesity is significantly associated with disabling conditions due to increased joint pressure from excess weight. It is also associated with mental health problems including anxiety and depression. Additionally, people with learning disabilities have a higher prevalence of obesity. Due to all the disabilities mentioned above, one who suffers from obesity can expect to face poor quality life considering they will come across all these disabilities in their everyday life making regular tasks fell harder than normal.(19,20)

1. **3.4 Economy and Obesity** - When it comes to these two terms, the impact is multifaced. Obese people alter the economy due to their condition as much as the economy itself has an impact on the individuals suffering from obesity. Direct medical costs as well as premature mortality, account for a crucial portion of the money spend per year to support obesity cases thus weakening the economy. Conversely, the economy can impact obese people as well. Economic factors such as income level, employment status, and labor protections affect access to healthcare, nutrition, and lifestyle choices, which can influence obesity prevalence and management. More precisely, the economy creates a feedback loop that by influencing their health directly and economic outcomes indirectly. In conclusion, the economy both affects and is affected by obesity.(21)

2. **3.5 Obesity's affect in life expectancy** is also a very crucial public health aspect which must be considered. As it's visible in Figure 1 and Figure 2 the color of the skin gives completely different results. In figure 1 is visible a pattern in which white men have a variability depended on years and BMI. White women have less noticeable variety. In both white men and women is presented a logic increase as the BMI gets higher. Completely different pattern is noted in black men and women, where obesity seems not affecting men and women with BMI less than 32 and the maximum affect is visible for black men with BMI >45 (about 20 years) and for black women with BMI >45 (about 5 years). (22)

Figure 1, (22)

Figure 2 (22)

In the scientific approach of obesity, we must note childhood obesity which is connected closely with adult obesity. There is a common belief in the world of science that if we can regulate childhood obesity, we can regulate adult obesity as well.(23)

When approaching **childhood obesity**, we must see it as a global epidemic leading to a serious public health problem. In WHO's COSI report published in 2025 a measurement of approximately 470.000 children across 37 countries shown that overall 25% of children (approximately 117.500 children) aged 7-9 years were living with overweight (including obesity) and 11% of children(approximately 51.700 children) live with obesity. So roughly 1 in 4 children are overweight and 1 in 10 are obese . Children with obesity tend more likely to become obesity adults. Children living with obesity are in a risky case of dealing with chronic diseases from a very young age. Fortunately, obesity and obesity are curable diseases, but it must be considered a good plan to prevent childhood obesity. The prevention must be measured in 3 levels: The primordial which is about keeping children in normal height and weight in their whole childhood period;

primary one which are actions done to prevent children from becoming obese and the secondary one which are measures used to prevent comorbidities in children and adults. (14,24–26)

4. CONCLUSION:

Now that we are aware of what obesity is, its public health aspects, which are linked in many factors. Factors like chronic health problems and illnesses like Diabetes, Cancer, MAFLD, Cardiovascular problems, Mental health problems, Factors like the effect in terms of mortality, life quality economy and life expectancy. We must give a battle with obesity before it is too late. Statistics in WHO's European region see that the numbers of obese people seem to be increasingly stable while in mortality rate WHO's European region is the only region which has a decreasing death rate every year. We hope every year statistics of people who are obese worldwide to get lower and eventually start their downfall and in terms of death rate the rest of WHO's regions take WHO's European region downfall way.

All the nations are informed and concerned about obesity, and they seem to do whatever is possible and in corporation with local and worldwide health organizations and institutes. If there was a good management of the health problem or it is needed further steps scientific society will have a chance to see that if compare with today's statistics. We are optimistic about the following years while we wait to see furthermore

new scientific updates and researches about obesity. We think humanity has the strength to fight against obesity and why not to eliminate it.

RECOMENDATONS:

- To fight against obesity is crucial to take numerus measures as society. Here are the recommendations:
 1. Expand on Regional Policy analysis, as we saw the management that WHO's European region has done so far is effective. It is considerable to realize how this effectiveness come from. Also direct comparison in terms of regional strategies is also considered effective as they focus in success on every single aspect.
 2. Highlight Research gaps, this will help understand everything about obesity and map every single aspect of it. This will also help to build better strategies against obesity
 3. Data renewal and Presentation, as shown in our research the lates data we had in our graphs were until 2021-22, so it is considered a necessity research society to renew the data in order to have better observation of obesity in terms of updates.
 4. Constant evaluation of already used policies in order to measure the outcomes and propose changes or new bettered policies
 5. Health authorities partner up with local communities, schools, and workplaces in order to promote health education and to customize their policies according to the tarageted nonulation's needs and culture.

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